

SafeHabitus

Anticipating Pathways to the Future of Farming:

***Impact of Climate Change on Future
Working Conditions and the Attractiveness
of Farming***

Deliverable 4.4

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Executive Summary

Context and Purpose

This deliverable builds on previous SafeHabitus research (D4.1, D4.2, D4.3) to examine how climate change is reshaping agricultural working conditions and the attractiveness of farming as a profession. Rising temperatures, extreme weather events, and shifting seasonal patterns create profound social and economic challenges for farmers and farm workers, including self-employed farmers, young entrants, seasonal and migrant workers. Addressing these challenges is essential to ensure generational renewal, rural sustainability, and long-term food security. This deliverable responds to Task 4.2's objective of supporting policy brief development (Milestone 15) through participatory foresight focused on young farmers, generational renewal, and climate change, and the implementation of a policy hackathon.

Methodology

SafeHabitus organised a two-day policy hackathon in Brussels with 32 stakeholders from research, policy, and practice—including farmers, young farmer representatives (CEJA), trade unions, policymakers, occupational health and safety experts and NGOs. On Day 1, participants used structured pair discussions followed by thematic clustering to identify ten key challenges related to climate change impacts on working conditions and farming attractiveness. Participants voted to select the top two challenges for in-depth analysis. Two working groups then developed roadmap-based solutions addressing: (1) lack of common understanding of climate change implications for farmers and farm businesses, including economic viability, and (2) policy integration with a focus on social protection in the context of climate change and farming. On Day 2, the SafeHabitus team synthesised these insights to inform subsequent policy analysis to assess links and gaps between the draft recommendations and current Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) 2027+ proposals. The results of this work will inform policy brief development in WP6.

Key Findings

Participants prioritised two interconnected challenges: (1) Lack of common societal understanding of climate change impacts on farming particularly in relation to the impacts on farmers, farm workers and medium-term socio-economic viability (17 votes), and (2) Inadequate integration of social protection into climate adaptation policies for agriculture (16 votes). Both working groups emphasised that climate change acts as a vulnerability multiplier, amplifying financial insecurity, mental health pressures, and occupational risks—particularly for farmers, including those with employees and those who are self-employed, new entrants, and seasonal and migrant workers. Critical policy gaps identified include fragmented governance across EU, national, and local levels; insufficient integration of occupational health and safety (OSH) into climate adaptation strategies; limited mechanisms supporting generational renewal and fair income distribution; and weak societal understanding of farming's role in climate resilience.

Policy Recommendations

Based on working group analyses, the hackathon generated multi-level policy recommendations:

- **EU level:** Establish an EU working group to assess feasibility of EU-wide OSH standards for agriculture, including climate-related protections; launch an EU-wide public education initiative on farming's role in climate solutions.
- **EU/National level:** Introduce flexibility mechanisms within CAP to allow Member States to adjust payment schedules following extreme weather events; ensure coordinated approaches integrating market tools, social protection, and OSH measures.
- **National level:** Develop or expand national crop-loss insurance schemes ensuring accessibility for small-scale farmers; establish national farmer mental health support programmes with climate-specific components; improve access to land and finance for young and new farmers.
- **Local/Sectoral level:** Strengthen rural service delivery (healthcare, childcare, transport, digital infrastructure) to improve quality of life and rural attractiveness.

Alignment with CAP Post-2027

The hackathon findings demonstrate strong alignment with the European Commission's July 2025 CAP 2027+ proposals, particularly regarding Member State flexibility for tailored interventions, enhanced support for generational renewal, integrated multi-level governance approaches, and provisions enabling farm relief services. These alignments validate the evidence-based, participatory methodology employed in D4.4 and confirm the policy relevance of stakeholder-identified priorities.

Importantly, the outcomes of the policy hackathon also identified critical gaps in current proposals, including the need for explicit integration of occupational health and safety measures within climate adaptation strategies and dedicated mental health support programmes for farmers. By both supporting emerging policy directions and highlighting areas requiring additional attention, this deliverable provides policy stakeholders with timely, actionable recommendations that respond to contemporary policy reform developments while identifying opportunities for enhancement.

Strategic Implications

These findings underscore that improving working conditions and sector attractiveness requires systemic change, connecting agricultural, social, and climate agendas to ensure fair economic conditions, occupational safety, and mental health support. Insights from this deliverable directly contribute to SafeHabitus Expected Outcomes 1 (enhanced understanding and awareness), 2 (improved policy and governance frameworks), and 4 (improved health, safety and labour conditions). The hackathon findings will inform development of policy briefs (Milestone 15), providing concrete, evidence-based recommendations for EU and national decision-makers to support resilient, equitable, and attractive farming futures.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Project Overview

The SafeHabitus project (2023–2026), funded by Horizon Europe, is a multi-actor research initiative dedicated to strengthening Farm Health and Safety Knowledge Innovation Systems and supporting the European Union’s transition toward socially sustainable farming. The project brings together a diverse network of stakeholders—including farmers, farm workers, researchers, advisors, trade unions, health authorities, and policymakers—to collaboratively address the pressing occupational health and safety challenges in agriculture.

One of the key focus areas of SafeHabitus is the impact of climate change on working conditions and the implications for the future attractiveness of farming as a profession. Rising temperatures, increasingly frequent extreme weather events, and shifting seasonal patterns are not only transforming agricultural production systems but also reshaping the food production and farm work. These changes disproportionately affect vulnerable groups such as young, seasonal, migrant, and self-employed farm workers, who can lack access to adequate protections, mental health support, and climate-resilient infrastructure.

To explore these challenges and co-create solutions, SafeHabitus organised a two-day social policy hackathon involving stakeholders from research, policy, and practice. Participants collaboratively identified key climate-related challenges, prioritised them through structured discussions and voting.

The project’s outcomes—including policy briefs and thematic analyses—are designed to inform EU and national decision-makers. By integrating climate adaptation with occupational health, and social equity, SafeHabitus contributes to building a resilient agricultural workforce and ensuring the long-term viability and attractiveness of farming in Europe.

1.2. The Objectives of Task 4.2

Task 4.2 aims to support the development of a policy brief (Milestone 15 – MS15) by facilitating a participatory foresight process culminating in a two-day policy hackathon. The results of the foresight process are reported in Deliverable 4.2. This work identified ‘climate change’ and ‘digitisation/automation’ as the fundamental drivers of change influencing future working conditions in agriculture. The hackathon engaged stakeholders from research and innovation (R&I), policy, and practice—including young farmers, self-employed farmers, employed farm workers, and representatives of vulnerable groups—to collaboratively explore future pathways for improving working conditions and wellbeing in agriculture.

The hackathon was designed to identify and assess the impacts of climate change on agricultural labour and to co-create policy responses that enhance the attractiveness of farming. Hackathon participants engaged in structured discussions to define key challenges, cluster and prioritise them, and develop roadmap-based analyses. These analysis results will serve as the foundation for building policy briefs. The decision to focus on climate change came from internal project discussions which concluded that the impacts of climate change represent an immediate disruption that will impact all farms and farmers. In contrast, technological disruption, whilst significant, will occur over a longer period in response to patterns of adoption and non-adoption, i.e. the impacts and implications will be socially and spatially differentiated.

The objective of this task was to translate stakeholder insights developed through the hackathon process into actionable policy recommendations that address climate-related vulnerabilities in farming. The resulting policy brief(s) will seek to inform EU and national-level decision-makers, focusing on inclusive, resilient, and sustainable approaches to agricultural labour and long-term food security.

1.3 Focus and Rationale: Building on Evidence from WP4 Deliverables

The focus on young farmers, generational renewal, and climate change in Deliverable 4.4 emerges directly from the evidence base established in earlier SafeHabitus deliverables, particularly D4.1, D4.2 and D4.3, creating a clear progression from problem identification to policy solution development.

Deliverable 4.1 provided foundational evidence that shaped the thematic focus and priorities of the D4.4 policy hackathon. Through a systematic literature review examining psychosocial challenges in agriculture and farming culture's impact on health and safety, D4.1 identified climate change as a critical driver affecting farmer mental health and wellbeing—insights that became central to the hackathon's problem identification processes.

Climate Change as a Key Stressor

D4.1's analysis highlighted that climate change poses psychological challenges for farmers, particularly through extreme weather events. The deliverable documented how increasing frequency and severity of droughts, floods, heat and other extreme weather events can create chronic stress and anxiety among farmers. This psychological burden manifests through multiple pathways: anticipatory anxiety about increasing precarity, financial stress from climate-induced losses, and cumulative impacts, both financial and personal, from repeated exposure to extreme weather events. D4.1 also identified that these mental health impacts can be intergenerational, as children grow up in environments characterised by stress and economic instability.

Vulnerable Populations and Compounded Stressors

The deliverable identified specific populations facing heightened vulnerabilities under climate change. Young farmers emerged as particularly at risk, facing economic insecurity intensified by limited resources for climate adaptation investments. D4.1 emphasised that climate stressors are "completely beyond the control of the individual," raising fundamental questions about collective societal responses and categorising them as "exceptional stressors" affecting resource management and family dynamics.

Structural and Policy Gaps

D4.1 revealed institutional challenges that informed the hackathon's policy focus. The deliverable documented how climate policies overlook the specific needs of farm workers, especially self-employed and family farm workers, while fragmentation between institutions hinders coordinated responses. Agricultural safety regulations were found to largely exclude climate-related working conditions despite their growing importance, with the effectiveness of voluntary safety standards questioned. The analysis revealed that mental health support remains systematically under-addressed in climate adaptation strategies, despite being fundamental to farmer wellbeing and sector attractiveness.

Translation to Hackathon Design

These findings from D4.1 informed the focus of D4.2, see below, and contributed to the hackathon's structure and priorities. The identification of climate change as a multi-dimensional stressor—affecting economic security, physical working conditions, mental health, and intergenerational continuity—shaped the hackathon's holistic approach to challenge identification. D4.1's emphasis on vulnerable populations ensured that the hackathon explicitly engaged young farmers, self-employed farmers, and representatives of migrant and seasonal workers as key participants. The documented policy gaps around mental health support, social protection systems, and occupational safety regulations became central themes in the hackathon's roadmap-based discussions, where participants explored barriers, existing initiatives, and necessary interventions. Ultimately, D4.1's evidence base validated the hackathon's focus on climate change as not merely an environmental or productivity issue, but as a fundamental challenge to the attractiveness of farming, requiring integrated policy responses that address economic, social, psychological, and institutional dimensions simultaneously.

D4.2: Establishing the Evidence Base

Deliverable 4.2 ("Visions of the future of farming: Implications for the attractiveness of farming and food security") provides comprehensive evidence demonstrating how climate change, generational renewal, and young farmers' concerns intersect as critical challenges for European agriculture. The deliverable explicitly identifies "Intergenerational Continuity" as a cross-cutting quality of life determinant, noting that the perceived viability of farming as a multigenerational enterprise significantly affects current farmer wellbeing. D4.2's foresight workshops identified "Financial Insecurity and Generational Renewal" as a key challenge

area, with climate change intensifying financial insecurity and creating barriers to young people entering farming through recurring impacts from extreme weather events, high stress levels, and low-income prospects. The deliverable also identified "Socio-Economic Insecurity and the Future of the Young Generation," emphasising how climate-induced uncertainty undermines young farmers' ability to envisage stable futures in agriculture.

D4.3: Centring Youth Perspectives

Deliverable 4.3 ("Youth perspectives of the future attractiveness of farming") provides additional qualitative insights from young and potential future farmers across the EU through focus group discussions organised in collaboration with the European Council of Young Farmers (CEJA). This deliverable explicitly addresses farm inheritance and succession, examining young farmers' responses to the future scenarios developed in D4.2. While D4.3 was not available for full review at the time of D4.4 development, its documented focus on young farmers' perspectives regarding farming's attractiveness, barriers to entry, and intergenerational dynamics provides the youth-centred evidence base that D4.4 draws on when considering assessing current policy proposals.

Synthesis for Policy Development

Together, D4.2 and D4.3 establish a rationale for D4.4's focus area. D4.2 demonstrates how climate change serves as a fundamental driver affecting all aspects of farming's future, which also influence the future attractiveness of farming. D4.3 complements this with bottom-up perspectives from young farmers themselves, showcasing how they experience and respond to these systemic challenges. D4.4 builds upon this foundation by engaging diverse stakeholders in co-creating policy pathways that address the interconnected challenges identified in earlier deliverables, with the objective of informing the development of policy briefs that support the attractiveness of farming (Milestone 15).

1.4 Contribution to SafeHabitus Expected Outcomes

Deliverable 4.4 directly contributes to the overall expected outcomes of the SafeHabitus project as specified in both the Grant Agreement and the Horizon Europe Call Topic (HORIZON-CL6-2022-COMMUNITIES-01-02). The call text emphasises that project results should foster sustainable, balanced, and inclusive development of rural areas, supporting implementation of the EU Farm to Fork Strategy, the European Pillar of Social Rights, and the Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas. Through its focus on young farmers, generational renewal, and climate change impacts, this deliverable advances all four expected outcomes (EO) outlined for the SafeHabitus project. This section briefly summarises how D4.4's policy hackathon findings and subsequent policy brief development directly advance, particularly, EO1, 2 and 4.

1.4.1 Expected Outcome 1: Enhanced Understanding and Awareness

Expected Outcome: *Enhanced understanding and awareness by policy makers, farmers organisations, trade unions and health authorities of farmers' and farm workers' health and safety, and on the implications of the perceptions of their work on the future of the sector and hence on long-term food security.*

D4.4 Contribution:

The policy hackathon methodology employed in D4.4 directly enhanced understanding among diverse stakeholders by bringing together policy makers, farmers' organisations, young farmers, farm workers, and researchers in structured dialogue. The hackathon's collaborative challenge identification process revealed critical gaps in awareness about how climate change intersects with occupational health and generational renewal. Specifically, D4.4 highlighted that:

- Young farmers face compounded vulnerabilities due to financial insecurity intensified by climate-induced losses, directly affecting their willingness to enter and remain in farming.
- Climate change threatens the attractiveness of farming by creating uncertainty about long-term viability, particularly impacting youth career decisions and farm succession planning.
- Current policy frameworks inadequately address the intersection of climate adaptation, mental health support, and generational renewal.
- Limited societal appreciation of farming work, combined with climate-related risks, undermines the sector's capacity to attract and retain new generations.

Through structured stakeholder engagement and evidence synthesis from prior deliverables (D4.1, D4.2, D4.3), D4.4 has supported increased awareness of how perceptions of farming's future—shaped by climate uncertainty—directly impact food security by influencing generational renewal. The deliverable translates this understanding into policy-relevant

insights that will inform the development of Milestone 15 (MS15), a policy brief(s) on measures to support farming's attractiveness.

1.4.2 Expected Outcome 2: Improved Policy and Governance Frameworks

Expected Outcome: *Improved policy and governance frameworks favouring safer and more inclusive working environments for farmers and farm workers.*

D4.4 Contribution:

D4.4's core purpose is to inform improved policy frameworks through multi-stakeholder co-creation of solutions. The hackathon's roadmap-based group work methodology enabled participants to systematically analyse policy gaps and develop recommendations across seven areas: problem definition, current situation analysis, target group identification, solution exploration, actor roles, implementation pathways, and impact indicators. This structured approach yielded actionable insights for policy improvement:

- Identification of critical gaps in EU and national policy frameworks regarding climate adaptation support for young farmers and new entrants.
- Recognition that current policies inadequately integrate occupational health and safety considerations with climate change adaptation strategies.
- Documentation of barriers to policy access faced by vulnerable groups, including young, seasonal, and migrant farm workers.
- Development of evidence-based recommendations for inclusive, integrated policy approaches that address climate resilience, mental health, and economic sustainability.
- Preliminary identification of governance levels (EU, national, regional) appropriate for different intervention types.

The deliverable's findings will directly inform policy brief development (MS15), providing decision-makers with co-created recommendations for improving governance frameworks. By considering young farmers and climate adaptation, D4.4 also addresses a critical policy gap identified across the SafeHabitus research: the need for integrated approaches that connect generational renewal support with climate resilience and occupational wellbeing.

1.4.3 Expected Outcome 4: Improved Health, Safety and Labour Conditions

Expected Outcome: *Improved health, safety and labour conditions in farming thanks to better performing European and national policy and legal frameworks and innovative bottom-up initiatives.*

D4.4 Contribution:

D4.4 makes a substantial contribution to this outcome through its explicit focus on how climate change impacts working conditions and through its bottom-up, participatory methodology. The hackathon identified specific climate-related health and safety challenges and co-created solutions with those directly affected:

- Documentation of how climate change exacerbates physical working conditions through extreme heat, unpredictable weather patterns, and increased exposure to health hazards.
- Recognition of mental health impacts on farmers—particularly young farmers—facing climate uncertainty, financial stress, and work-life balance challenges.
- Identification of gaps in current occupational health and safety frameworks regarding climate adaptation, with specific attention to vulnerable worker groups (young, self-employed, seasonal, migrant etc.).
- Co-creation of actionable solutions combining top-down policy improvements with bottom-up community initiatives.
- Emphasis on inclusive representation in policy-making processes to ensure that diverse farmer voices—especially young farmers and marginalised groups—shape future frameworks.

By focusing on young farmers and generational renewal in the context of climate change, D4.4 addresses a forward-looking dimension of occupational health: ensuring that the next generation of farmers can work under safer, healthier, and more socially sustainable conditions. The deliverable's findings emphasise that improving working conditions is not merely a matter of present-day worker protection but a strategic imperative for EU agricultural and social policies ensuring the agricultural sector's future viability, attractiveness and long-term food security.

1.4.4 Conclusion: D4.4 as a Strategic Deliverable

Deliverable 4.4 occupies a strategic position within the SafeHabitus project. By bringing together insights from earlier deliverables (D4.1's analysis of climate impacts on farmer mental health, D4.2's foresight scenarios, D4.3's youth perspectives) and engaging diverse stakeholders in solution co-creation, D4.4 supports the process of translating research findings into policy-relevant recommendations. The deliverable's focus on young farmers, generational renewal, and climate change addresses a set of related challenges that will strongly shape European agriculture's future sustainability, resilience, and social viability.

Through inclusive stakeholder engagement, and building on evidence developed with WP4, D4.4 directly advances three of the four expected outcomes, i.e. EO1, 2 & 4, of the SafeHabitus project. The subsequent policy brief(s) developed from these findings (MS15) will provide concrete tools for EU and national decision-makers to strengthen farm health and safety knowledge innovation systems, enhance the capacity for bottom-up solutions,

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and ensure that European agriculture can attract, support, and retain the next generation of farmers in an era of climate change.

2. Literature Review: Climate Change, Working Conditions, and Farming Attractiveness

This chapter provides the evidence base underpinning the focus of Deliverable 4.4 on climate change, working conditions, and the attractiveness of farming as a profession. The rationale for this focus emerges from a growing body of research and previous SafeHabitus deliverables (D4.1, D4.2, D4.3), which collectively demonstrate that climate change is not only an environmental challenge but also a profound social and economic stressor for European agriculture. Rising temperatures, extreme weather events, and shifting seasonal patterns are transforming production systems and reshaping farm work. These changes affect everyone working in agriculture, from self-employed farmers, through to new entrants, seasonal and migrant workers, and employers.

The literature consistently highlights three interconnected dimensions:

- **Physical and Occupational Risks:** Climate change increases exposure to heat stress, unpredictable weather, and health hazards, undermining safety and productivity.
- **Mental Health and Wellbeing:** Extreme weather events and financial uncertainty create chronic stress and anxiety among farmers, with intergenerational impacts documented in rural communities.
- **Attractiveness of Farming and Generational Renewal:** Economic insecurity and harsh working conditions discourage young people from entering farming, threatening succession, generational renewal and long-term food security.

By synthesising insights from academic studies and prior SafeHabitus research, this review establishes why climate change and generational renewal are critical priorities for policy. It also identifies gaps in current EU and national frameworks, particularly the lack of integration between climate adaptation, occupational health, and social protection measures. These findings informed the design of the policy hackathon and shaped the thematic focus of Deliverable 4.4.

2.1. Climate Change and Working Conditions in Agriculture

Climate change is increasingly reshaping the agricultural sector, not only in terms of production methods but also in how farmers and farm workers work. Rising temperatures, more frequent extreme weather events, and shifting seasonal patterns are forcing changes in work schedules, such as night-time farming to avoid heat stress (Pogačar et al., 2019; Morris, Piil, et al., 2021). Despite these growing challenges, climate policies often overlook the specific needs of farm workers—especially those who are self-employed or part of farm

families (Huq and Hugé, 2010). At the policy level, fragmentation between institutions and a lack of coordination hinder the development of inclusive responses (Concu et al., 2020). Cultural norms, economic pressures, and limited access to training and support services further complicate adaptation efforts (Mertz et al., 2009). In addition, climate change has emerged as a major stressor affecting the mental health and well-being of farmers, yet mental health remains under-addressed in climate adaptation strategies (Lund et al., 2018; Becot, Kohlbeck and Ruszkowski, 2023). To ensure a fair and sustainable transition and underpin the medium- and long-term competitiveness of EU agriculture, it is important to consider how climate change affects different categories of farm workers and to develop targeted support systems that address their unique vulnerabilities.

2.1.1. Employed Farmers and Farm Workers

Employed farmers and farm workers—including seasonal and migrant labourers—represent one of the most vulnerable groups in European agriculture when facing climate change impacts. This group was considered separately in Deliverable 4.4 to highlight the similarities and differences in challenges compared to self-employed and young farmers, as identified in previous SafeHabitus research (D4.1). Extreme weather events such as heatwaves, floods, and droughts directly affect their working conditions, productivity, and income stability. Seasonal and migrant workers are particularly exposed due to precarious employment arrangements, limited access to social protection, and dependence on short-term contracts.

Climate change amplifies these vulnerabilities by potentially increasing physical risks (heat stress, unpredictable weather), economic insecurity (loss of working hours or jobs during climate-induced disruptions), and psychosocial pressures. Evidence from D4.1 and recent studies shows that these workers often lack adequate occupational health measures and mental health support, despite facing high stress levels linked to climate uncertainty and financial precarity. Mental health challenges—including anxiety and depression—are compounded by isolation, cultural barriers, and limited access to rural healthcare services (Lund et al., 2018; Becot et al., 2023; SafeHabitus D4.1).

Policy frameworks remain fragmented. While some protections exist for employed workers through both national and EU directives, many seasonal and migrant workers fall outside these systems, leaving significant gaps in occupational safety and social security (Castillo-Rojas-Marcos & Molinero-Gerbeau, 2024). Climate adaptation strategies rarely integrate labour rights or mental health considerations, creating a disconnect between environmental and social policy objectives.

These findings informed the hackathon's focus on inclusive solutions and highlighted the need for integrated approaches that combine climate resilience with occupational health and social protection. Addressing these gaps is essential to ensure that employed farm workers can adapt safely and sustainably to climate change, while maintaining the attractiveness of farming as a profession.

2.1.2. Self-employed Farmers

Self-employed farmers, many of whom are also employers, are the largest single group of workers involved in agricultural production across Europe, yet they face distinct and often overlooked challenges in adapting to climate change. Unlike employed farm workers, most operate without the safety net of employer-backed protections, i.e. agriculture related, social insurance, or institutional support. This leaves them exposed to the economic and health consequences of climate-related disruptions, with limited access to formal assistance or compensation mechanisms.

Economically, self-employed farmers are highly vulnerable. Crop failures or extreme weather events—such as droughts, floods, and heatwaves—can lead to substantial income loss. At the same time, the pressure to invest in climate-resilient technologies, e.g. smart irrigation systems, automation, and drought-resistant crops, can result in additional financial strain or need to avail of loans (Parra-López et al., 2024). Although they may have flexibility in scheduling their work, such as shifting to night hours to avoid heat stress, they still face comparable physical and mental health risks as employed workers (Morris, Levi, et al., 2021).

Mental health support for self-employed farmers/employers is especially lacking (SafeHabitus D4.1). These individuals bear the full weight of decision-making, financial risk, and operational stress, yet they are frequently excluded from structured mental health programmes and rural healthcare services, which are typically linked to social insurance systems (Shortland et al., 2023; Shortall and Barillà, 2024). This exclusion contributes to increased stress, isolation, and reduced well-being, particularly in remote farming communities.

Policy frameworks often do not recognise the challenges faced by self-employed farmers. Occupational health and safety regulations are generally designed for employed workers, and both national and EU level sectoral consultation processes do not always include self-employed voices. As a result, their needs and perspectives can be underrepresented in climate adaptation policymaking (Shortall and Barillà, 2024). Addressing this gap requires inclusive policy spaces at both national and EU levels, where self-employed farmers can actively participate in shaping the regulations that affect them.

Digital technologies offer promising tools for climate resilience, but adoption is hindered by several barriers. Rural infrastructure gaps, high costs, and limited digital literacy restrict access to smart farming solutions (Samadder, Pandya and Lal, 2023; Parra-López et al., 2024). Financial incentives such as grants and low-interest loans could help overcome these barriers (Sheik, 2023), while simplified interfaces and localised training would make digital tools more accessible to small-scale producers (Marshall et al., 2022).

In conclusion, supporting self-employed farmers in the face of climate change requires a multi-dimensional approach. Inclusive policies, targeted financial and health assistance, and equitable access to innovation are essential to ensure their resilience and sustainability.

Without these measures, their ability to adapt and sustain their livelihoods will remain at risk, undermining the stability of rural economies and the broader agricultural sector.

2.1.3. Young Farmers

Young farmers are a critical group for the future of European agriculture, yet they remain significantly underrepresented in climate adaptation policies and occupational health frameworks. Deliverable D4.4 considered this group separately to reflect findings from earlier SafeHabitus research (D4.1, D4.2, D4.3), which identified generational renewal as a key challenge for sector sustainability. Climate change intensifies these challenges by increasing financial insecurity, reducing resilience, and creating uncertainty about farming's long-term viability.

Evidence from D4.2 and D4.3 shows that young farmers face structural barriers to entry, including limited access to land, credit, and training opportunities. Their economic vulnerability mirrors that of self-employed farmers but is compounded by intergenerational expectations and family care responsibilities, which may restrict flexibility in adopting climate-resilient practices (Rose et al., 2023; Ullah et al., 2024). These constraints can lead to stress and social isolation, as documented in D4.1 and supported by studies on rural mental health (Lund et al., 2018; Becot et al., 2023). Mental health challenges—such as anxiety and depression—are exacerbated by uncertainty about succession and the perceived unattractiveness of farming as a career.

Policy gaps further undermine resilience. Young farmers are frequently excluded from formal consultation processes and occupational health protections, which are typically designed for employed workers. While organizations like CEJA provide representation, their strategic interests are not consistently reflected in national or EU-level decisions (Shortall & Barillà, 2024). This disconnect limits the effectiveness of climate adaptation strategies and perpetuates generational renewal challenges.

These findings informed the hackathon's emphasis on inclusive policy design and targeted support for young farmers. Participants recognised that addressing economic insecurity, mental health, and access to innovation is essential to make farming an attractive and sustainable profession for future generations. Without integrated measures, the resilience of this group—and the continuity of European agriculture—will remain at risk.

2.1.4. Attractiveness of Farming as a Profession in the Context of Climate Change

The attractiveness of farming as a profession is a cornerstone of generational renewal and rural sustainability. However, evidence from SafeHabitus deliverables (D4.1, D4.2, D4.3) and recent studies shows that climate change undermines attractiveness by reducing job quality and working conditions and increasing economic uncertainty. Rising temperatures, more frequent heatwaves, and unpredictable weather patterns increase physical strain and health risks, including mental health, for farmers, while extreme events such as floods and droughts

disrupt production cycles and income stability. These pressures make farming less appealing to younger generations, who perceive the sector as high-risk and low-reward compared to other career options (Rose et al., 2023; Ma & Rahut, 2024; Holton et al., 2023; Shortall & Barillà, 2024; Ullah et al., 2024).

D4.2 highlighted that financial insecurity and climate-induced volatility are key deterrents for youth considering farming careers. D4.3 reinforced this by documenting young farmers' concerns about succession, work-life balance, and mental health under climate stress. These findings align with broader research indicating that job quality in agriculture—measured by income security, occupational safety, and social recognition—lags behind other sectors (Shortall & Barillà, 2024). Without targeted interventions, these trends undermine generational renewal and the long-term viability of European agriculture.

Policy frameworks have not adequately addressed this challenge. While climate adaptation strategies focus on environmental resilience, they rarely integrate measures to improve working conditions or demonstrate/enhance the social value of farming. Mental health support, fair remuneration for ecosystem services, and inclusive decision-making remain underdeveloped. These gaps informed the hackathon's emphasis on systemic solutions that link climate resilience with occupational health and social sustainability.

3. Methodology: Social Hackathon- Exploring the Impact of Climate Change on Future Working Conditions and the Attractiveness of Farming

3.1. Purpose and Approach

To explore the complex relationship between climate change, agricultural working conditions, and the attractiveness of farming as a profession, the SafeHabitus project organised a two-day policy hackathon in Brussels. This event served as a central methodological activity within Task 4.2, designed to foster multi-actor collaboration and generate policy-relevant insights. The hackathon brought together stakeholders from research, policy, and practice to engage in structured dialogue, challenge identification, and strategic planning. Through participatory formats—including pair discussions, thematic clustering, roadmap-based group work, and internal policy brief preparation—the hackathon enabled a holistic examination of climate-related vulnerabilities in agriculture and laid the groundwork for future policy development. Reflecting this, the overarching goal was to generate actionable insights and recommendations that could inform EU and national-level strategies for improving the resilience, safety, and inclusivity of the agricultural workforce.

3.2. Participant Recruitment and Data Collection

3.2.1 Recruitment Approach

Participants were recruited through a combination of strategies, including direct invitations to SafeHabitus consortium members and associated experts, as well as targeted outreach to key stakeholder organisations such as farmers, policy stakeholders, trade unions, farmers' organisations, and networks representing young farmers. Invitations were also extended to EU-level institutions, national policymakers, and occupational safety bodies to ensure broad representation and diverse knowledge expertise was available to inform the discussion.

3.2.2 Selection Criteria

The recruitment process aimed to achieve balance across stakeholder types—farmers (both self-employed and employed), farm workers, researchers, policymakers, trade union

representatives, and farming organisations—while ensuring geographical diversity across EU Member States. Gender balance and inclusion of different age groups were also considered. Final selection prioritised diversity of perspectives and active involvement in agricultural policy or practice.

3.3.3 Response and Engagement

Most invited participants confirmed attendance, including representatives from farming organisations, trade unions, EU institutions, and national bodies. Some invitees who could not attend in full contributed through plenary sessions, while others who were unable to attend personally delegated their colleagues to participate on their behalf.

3.3.4 Participant Representation Overview

The composition of participants by category and examples of organisations represented is summarised below:

Table 1. Participant Representation by Category and Key Organizations

Category	Structure, %	Organizations
Researchers / Academia	40%	Vytautas Magnus University, Teagasc, ILVO, Newcastle University, Luke, CIHEAM Zaragoza, Lucian Blaga University of Sibiu
Farmers & Farming Organisations	20%	ASAJA, CEJA, KB Bendras Ūkis, Agrikids
EU Institutions & Policymakers	20%	DG AGRI, EESC (European Economic and Social Committee), European Committee of the Regions, EP AGRI
Trade Unions	5%	EFFAT
Occupational Safety & Health Bodies	10%	Prevent Agri, EU-OSHA
Communications / Press	5%	AEIDL

3.3.5 Ethics and Data Collection Approach

The policy hackathon was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles established in the SafeHabitus Grant Agreement and in compliance with Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR) on the protection of personal data. Prior to participation, all attendees were provided with information about the research objectives and data handling procedures, and informed consent was obtained from all 32 stakeholders. To protect participant anonymity, particularly given the candid nature of policy discussions involving representatives from diverse institutional contexts, no direct quotations from the event are attributed to individual participants in this report. Sessions were documented through detailed note-taking by dedicated rapporteurs assigned to each working group. Audio recordings were used to support post-event synthesis and accuracy checking. Recordings were transcribed after the

event, and all transcripts were fully anonymised prior to analysis. No verbatim quotations are used in this report, and transcripts were used exclusively for thematic aggregation rather than attribution of individual statements. Visual outputs, including thematic clustering boards and policy roadmaps developed during collaborative exercises, were photographed with participant consent. Audio recordings were made to ensure accuracy in synthesising complex multi-stakeholder discussions; however, these recordings captured only the substance of discussions, and no personal information was retained. The results of the workshops were summarised and further evaluated with the support of artificial intelligence (AI). Details of how the AI was used and the process it followed are given in Annex 1. All research materials, including notes, photographs, and audio files, are securely stored in the VDU's (Task leader) SafeHabitus project repository with access restricted to authorised VDU members, in accordance with the project's data management protocols.

3.3. Collaborative Challenge Identification

The first day of the hackathon began with a series of introductory presentations, including a brief overview of the SafeHabitus project by the Project Leader, Dr David Meredith, and a thematic briefing on the impact of climate change on farm workers from Dr Salvatore Barillà. These presentations set the stage for the collaborative work that followed. Participants were then invited to form pairs—ten in total—and engage in focused discussions aimed at identifying two key challenges related to the impact of climate change on future working conditions and the attractiveness of farming. Each pair was provided with two coloured stickers, one for each challenge, and asked to write down their selected issues. These discussions lasted approximately 10 minutes, encouraging concise and targeted reflection.

Following the pair discussions, each duo presented their challenges to the full group, briefly explaining the rationale behind their selections. This presentation phase was carefully timed, allowing up to 5 minutes per pair, resulting in a total of 20 proposed topics – many of which were either similar or related to other topics. Next, the facilitator led a thematic clustering exercise, grouping the stickers on a large board based on common themes and areas of concern. This step helped visualise the collective priorities and facilitated a shared understanding of the challenge landscape, as well as led to the creation of a list of topics for voting and for further group discussion (10 topics). To determine which challenges would be explored in greater depth, participants engaged in a voting session. Each individual was given two small voting stickers and asked to select the challenges they considered most critical. The two topics receiving the highest number of votes were selected for further analysis during the group work sessions later in the day.

After the event, to enhance analytical clarity while preserving the authenticity of participant contributions, a two-stage analytical approach was employed. First, the ten challenges were systematically coded against five cross-cutting themes that emerged inductively from the data: (T1) Economic/Financial Vulnerability; (T2) Social Protection Gaps; (T3) Generational Renewal; (T4) Health and Psychosocial Wellbeing; and (T5) Policy Coordination. Each challenge was mapped against these themes to identify where multiple challenges engage with common underlying structural issues. This mapping is presented in the results section

(Table 2). Second, a synthesis was developed that integrates insights across the ten challenges, organised around the five cross-cutting themes. This synthesis highlights the systemic relationships between challenges—for example, how economic vulnerability (T1) drives both mental health impacts (T4) and generational renewal problems (T3)—rather than treating each challenge in isolation. This approach is important in delving deeper into the data that were collected and supports identification of points where integrated policy responses could address multiple challenges simultaneously. The detailed challenge descriptions (Annex 2) preserved the original framing and emphasis from hackathon participants, ensuring that the analysis remained grounded in stakeholder perspectives while the synthesis provided in the Results chapter supports not only a better understanding of the interrelated nature of challenges and the richness of the discussion, but also an interpretive framework that will support development of the policy brief(s).

This structured, participatory process ensured that the challenges prioritised for deeper exploration were not only relevant but also agreed by a diverse group of stakeholders. It showcased the SafeHabitus project's multi-actor, engaged research approach and provided a foundation for the roadmap-based discussions that followed.

3.4. Thematic Group Work

Following the prioritisation of challenges, participants were divided into two thematic groups, each tasked with exploring one of the selected topics in depth. The groups were composed to reflect a multi-actor approach, ensuring representation from farmers, researchers, policymakers, and other key stakeholders. This diversity enabled a comprehensive and wide-ranging analysis of the issues identified at the first stage.

Each group engaged in a 90-minute structured discussion guided by a facilitator and supported by a notetaker. The discussions followed a predefined roadmap framework consisting of seven analytical dimensions (Figure 1). This figure illustrates the framework applied to guide the group work sessions of the SafeHabitus social hackathon. In practice, this took the form of a large poster that enabled participants to follow the process from one stage to the next whilst also facilitating iterative updates as they did so (Figure 2). The roadmap was printed and placed on large tables to facilitate collaborative input using stickers and markers. Participants contributed ideas directly onto the roadmap, enabling visual clustering and synthesis of perspectives. By guiding participants through seven interconnected dimensions—from problem definition to indicators of success—the roadmap ensured a comprehensive and systematic exploration of climate-related challenges in agriculture. It also supported multi-actor dialogue and helped translate diverse perspectives into policy-relevant insights. After the group discussions, each team presented their findings in a plenary session, followed by a joint moderated discussion to consolidate insights and identify cross-cutting themes. This process ensured that the outcomes were not only well-informed but also collectively validated.

Figure 1. Social Hackathon Roadmap: From Problem Identification to Impact Evaluation

3.5. Co-Creation of Policy Insights and Policy Mapping

The second day of the hackathon was dedicated to internal work by the SafeHabitus team, focusing on how to translate the insights and findings from Day 1 into structured policy briefs. Building on the outcomes of the roadmap-based group discussions, the team engaged in a collaborative session to explore the strategic application of these findings in future policy development (Figure 3). This session involved nine members of the SafeHabitus consortium, including representatives from VDU, CEJA, TEAGASC, UNEW, LUKE, and IAMZ-CIHEAM. All discussions were documented through detailed notes, with informed consent provided verbally by all participants.

The day began with a roundtable review of all materials from Day 1, including:

- Presentation of an overview of challenges identified by participants.

Impact of Climate Change on Working Conditions and Sectoral Attractiveness

Figure 2. Roadmap framework structuring thematic group activities

- Summary of notes from the voting process and plenary discussions.
- Assessment of the 'roadmaps' from both working groups.

This review ensured that the next stage of the assessment of the outcomes of the hackathon was grounded in stakeholder priorities and evidence from Day 1 (see below).

Figure 3. Social Hackathon Day 2

An important dimension of the Day 2 internal session involved examining how the hackathon findings related to emerging European policy frameworks, particularly the Common Agricultural Policy proposals for the post-2027 period. In July 2025, shortly before the Brussels hackathon, the European Commission published its legislative proposals for the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) 2028–2034, marking a significant evolution in EU agricultural policy (European Commission, 2025a). The timing of the hackathon coincided with a key window for policy dialogue, as these proposals entered parliamentary and stakeholder review processes. It also provided a framework against which the project team could assess the extent to which the topics, issues and policy suggestions raised during the hackathon could be assessed in terms of their coverage. The initial round of ‘benchmarking’ occurred during Day 1 with policy stakeholders, in particular asked to indicate if they knew of relevant policy measures linked to the issues that were raised. During Day 2, there was further discussion of potential links between current and proposed policies. Finally, during the analysis and drafting stage of the report, this information was used as a starting point to assess links to or gaps in the CAP policy. The mapping exercise reflected the project’s commitment to policy-engaged research. Rather than developing recommendations in

isolation from current policy development processes, the hackathon findings were situated within contemporary policy development processes. This approach ensured that D4.4 outcomes would be relevant to decision-makers navigating CAP development and could inform both EU-level regulatory refinement and Member State strategic plan development. The identification of alignments and gaps positioned the SafeHabitus research as engaging and supporting policy development.

3.6. Research Limitations

This study employed a participatory hackathon methodology involving 32 stakeholders to explore climate change impacts on agricultural working conditions and farming attractiveness. While this approach generated valuable policy-relevant insights, several limitations warrant acknowledgment.

Methodological Constraints

The two-day timeframe, while enabling intensive engagement, constrained the depth of exploration possible for each challenge area. The structured roadmap approach prioritised breadth across multiple dimensions over extended deliberation on specific topics. Additionally, the hackathon format emphasised solution generation rather than systematic validation of proposed interventions, meaning recommendations reflect stakeholder perspectives rather than evidence-tested efficacy.

Participant Representation

Although recruitment aimed for diversity across stakeholder types, Member States, and demographics, certain groups remained underrepresented. Seasonal and migrant workers—identified in the literature as particularly vulnerable to climate impacts—had limited direct representation, with their perspectives mediated primarily through trade union delegates and researchers. Geographic representation skewed toward participants from Western and Northern Europe, potentially limiting insights into Mediterranean and Eastern European agricultural contexts where climate impacts manifest differently (Ciscar et al., 2021; Toreti et al., 2024).

Generalisability Concerns

The Brussels location may have influenced both who participated and the policy framing adopted. Stakeholders with proximity to EU institutions and policy processes were likely overrepresented relative to those working primarily at farm or community levels. Consequently, recommendations reflect policy-engaged perspectives but may not fully capture on-farm realities or grassroots adaptation strategies (Mitter et al., 2023). The inclusion of both farmers and farmer representatives sought to overcome this limitation.

Data Collection and Analysis

While anonymisation protocols protected participant confidentiality, they also precluded tracking how different stakeholder categories contributed to specific recommendations, limiting analysis of potential divergences between, for example, farmer and policymaker perspectives.

4. Results

The preceding chapters established the evidence base linking climate change to agricultural working conditions/job quality, drawing on findings from Deliverables D4.1, D4.2, and D4.3, and detailed the participatory methodology employed during the policy hackathon. Building on this foundation, this chapter presents the results. These are organised into two main sections. Section 4.1 reports the climate-driven challenges identified through structured pair discussions and thematic clustering. Section 4.2 then presents findings from the roadmap-based group discussions, where participants developed detailed analyses and identified potential policy recommendations. Together, these outputs provide the empirical foundation for translating stakeholder insights into the policy brief(s) development planned for Milestone 15.

4.1. Collaborative Identification of Climate-Driven Challenges

The hackathon discussions emphasised that while climate change is widely recognised as a pressing global issue, the implications for farming livelihoods and working conditions remain unevenly understood and inadequately addressed. The identification of these challenges is an important step toward developing coherent, inclusive, and forward-looking policy responses (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Collaborative Challenge Identification

During this exploratory phase participants highlighted that climate change not only threatens agricultural productivity and environmental sustainability, which are generally well understood, but also the social and economic viability of rural communities. This, in turn, has implications for the future attractiveness of farming as a profession which is being undermined by financial insecurity that is amplified through the impacts of extreme weather events, low societal appreciation for the business and personal implications of these impacts on farmers and farm families, and, in some areas, limited institutional capacity to respond to climate impacts. These overarching themes formed the structure around which the participants clustered, see section 3.3, the original 20 issues into ten challenge areas (Figure 5). These are described below.

Figure 5. Key Challenge Areas that Climate Change Poses for the Agricultural Sector (created by AI)

4.1.2 Challenge–Theme Matrix

Table 2 presents the mapping of the ten hackathon challenges against five cross-cutting themes. Shaded cells (●) indicate that the challenge engages substantively with the theme. The matrix highlights that economic/financial vulnerability (T1) is the most pervasive theme, featuring in seven of ten challenges, while social protection gaps (T2) and policy coordination (T5) emerge as structural issues that shape the policy landscape within which other challenges manifest.

Table 2. Mapping key challenges to cross-cutting themes

Challenge	Economic/Financial Vulnerability	Social Protection Gaps	Generational Renewal	Health & Wellbeing	Policy Coordination
C1: Shared understanding of climate change	•				•
C2: Policy integration (agricultural, social, employment)		•			•
C3: Financial insecurity & generational renewal	•		•		
C4: Insurance & support mechanisms	•	•			•
C5: Public perceptions of farming			•	•	
C6: Economic & occupational risks of workers	•	•		•	
C7: Farmer mental health & value recognition	•		•	•	
C8: Socio-economic insecurity & youth futures	•		•		
C9: Health, well-being & work–life balance		•		•	
C10: Managing uncertainty in operations	•				

4.2. Synthesis: Structural Issues Underlying the Ten Challenges

The ten challenges identified through the policy hackathon, while presented as discrete issues, are reflective of deeper structural tensions in European agriculture that climate change is intensifying. This synthesis draws together insights across challenges to illuminate these underlying dynamics and their implications for policy.

4.2.1 Economic and Financial Vulnerability as a Cross-Cutting Driver

Economic vulnerability emerged as the most pervasive theme across the hackathon discussions, featuring explicitly in seven of the ten challenges (C1, C3, C4, C6, C7, C8, C10). Participants consistently identified a reinforcing cycle: climate-induced production losses reduce farm income; reduced income constrains investment in adaptation measures; inadequate adaptation increases vulnerability to subsequent climate events. This cycle is compounded by structural features of agricultural markets—including price volatility, concentration in supply chains, and what participants characterised as 'unfair competition'—that predate climate change but are being amplified by it.

The economic dimension extends beyond farm-level income to encompass the broader viability of agricultural livelihoods. Participants noted that agricultural earnings average approximately 40% below other sectors, a disparity that undermines the sector's capacity to attract and retain workers. When combined with climate-related income instability, this baseline disadvantage makes farming increasingly unattractive, particularly to younger generations who observe recurring financial stress among established farmers.

4.2.2 Structural Gaps in Social Protection Frameworks

A critical structural issue identified across challenges C2, C4, and C6 concerns the fundamental architecture of social protection in European agriculture. The majority of EU farmers are self-employed, yet existing EU occupational safety and health (OSH) directives establish protections within employer–employee relationships. This creates a regulatory gap whereby most farmers fall outside the scope of OSH frameworks entirely—not just those related to climate-specific provisions, limited though these currently are.

Participants emphasised that the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), while providing essential income support, was not designed to function as a social protection instrument. This leaves a significant policy gap: agricultural income support operates through one framework CAP, occupational safety through another (OSH directives), and social security through Member State systems, with limited coordination between them. Climate change impacts—which simultaneously affect income, working conditions, and health—expose the limitations of this fragmented approach, as farmers experience compounding risks that no single policy domain adequately addresses.

4.2.3 Generational Renewal and Sectoral Attractiveness

The interconnection between climate impacts and generational renewal emerged strongly across challenges C3, C5, C7, and C8. Participants articulated a clear causal pathway: young people observe established farmers experiencing pressure/stress resulting from climate-induced losses, and uncertain income prospects; this observation influences their assessment of farming as a viable career; which in turn may result in reluctance to enter agriculture and threatens the long-term sustainability of food production and rural communities.

Importantly, participants framed generational renewal not solely as an economic calculation but as a question of whether young people can envisage a stable and fulfilling future in farming. This encompasses material security but extends to social recognition, work–life balance, and sense of purpose. The public perception challenges identified in C5—whereby farming's positive contributions to food security and environmental stewardship are underrepresented—compound the attractiveness problem by limiting potential entrants the social validation that might offset economic uncertainties.

4.2.4 Health, Wellbeing, and Psychosocial Sustainability

Challenges C6, C7, and C9 collectively highlight the health and psychosocial dimensions of climate change in agriculture. Physical health risks are intensifying as rising temperatures, heat stress, and extreme weather events directly affect outdoor working conditions. However, participants placed equal or greater emphasis on mental health impacts: the psychological burden of managing increasing uncertainty, experiencing repeated losses, and confronting an uncertain future for one's livelihood and community.

The concept of work–life balance featured prominently, with participants noting that growing workloads which are, for the most part, independent of climate change, but exacerbated by climate-related pressures increasingly compromise farmers' capacity to maintain healthy boundaries between work and personal life. This has implications not only for individual wellbeing but for community cohesion and quality of life in rural areas. The Finnish model of farmer support—encompassing medical and health insurance alongside respite services enabling farmers to take holidays—was cited as demonstrating that comprehensive approaches to farmer wellbeing are both possible and effective.

4.2.5 Policy Fragmentation and Coordination Failures

Challenges C1, C2, and C4 explicitly address policy coordination, but this theme implicitly underlies the entire set of challenges. Participants identified fragmentation operating at multiple levels: between EU, national, and local governance; across policy domains (agricultural, social, employment, health); and between different instruments within domains (e.g., CAP income support versus risk management tools). This fragmentation undermines the development of strategic responses to climate-related risks, which by their nature cut across traditional policy boundaries.

The absence of a shared understanding of climate change across levels and stakeholders (C1) both reflects and reinforces coordination failures. Without common framing, priorities diverge and collective action becomes difficult. Participants emphasised that addressing climate impacts on agricultural working conditions requires not only strengthening individual policy instruments but fundamentally improving coordination mechanisms—between levels of governance, across policy domains, and between public authorities and stakeholder communities.

4.2.6. Implications for Policy Response

This synthesis reveals that the ten challenges identified through the hackathon are not independent problems requiring separate solutions, but interconnected elements of structural vulnerabilities that climate change is exposing and intensifying. Economic vulnerability drives health impacts and discourages generational renewal; social protection gaps leave farmers exposed when climate events occur; policy fragmentation limits coordinated response to risks that span multiple domains.

This systemic perspective has important implications for policy design. Interventions that address only isolated symptoms—for instance, providing additional income support without addressing OSH coverage gaps, or promoting farming careers without tackling underlying economic precarity—are unlikely to achieve lasting impact. Effective response requires integrated approaches that recognise how economic, social, health, and policy dimensions interact. The draft recommendations that follow (Section 4.4) are accordingly structured around these cross-cutting themes rather than the individual challenges, identifying leverage points where coordinated intervention could generate benefits across multiple problem areas. Before considering these issues however, we first provide an overview of the results of the roadmap-based discussions.

4.3. Roadmap-Based Group Discussions

After identifying the key climate-related challenges affecting the future working conditions and attractiveness of farming, participants were invited to vote by using two stickers to mark their two preferred challenges (Figure 6). Following the voting exercise, the two challenges receiving the highest number of votes: 1. Lack of common understanding of climate change and Economic Viability (17 votes) and 2. Policy integration with a focus on social protection in the context of climate change and farming (16 votes) were selected for the Priority Challenges session. The remaining eight challenges received substantially fewer votes each. This distribution is analytically significant: rather than selecting individual symptoms, participants collectively identified the two foundational structural issues that underpin the broader challenge landscape. The first priority reflects elements of Themes T1 (Economic/Financial Vulnerability) and T5 (Policy Coordination)—addressing both the basis of farming precarity and the fragmented understanding that impedes coherent response. The second priority reflects elements of Themes T2 (Social Protection Gaps) and T5 (Policy Coordination)—foregrounding the structural exclusion of self-employed farmers from occupational safety and health frameworks and the lack of integration between agricultural, social, and employment policy domains. That participants intuitively gravitated toward these root causes rather than downstream manifestations—such as mental health impacts (C7) or public perceptions (C5), which received limited number of votes—suggests a sophisticated understanding among stakeholders that effective intervention requires addressing underlying structural conditions. The roadmap discussions that followed, see below, focused on these points of influence and considered implementation pathways that could generate benefits across multiple challenge areas.

According to the logic presented in Section 3.4. the participants were divided into two thematic groups with each focusing on one of the priority areas with the discussion following the structured process outlined in Figure 1, i.e. Problem Definition, Target Group, Policy Gaps, Proposed Interventions, Implementation Pathways, Risks & Barriers, and Indicators of Success.

Figure 6. Roadmap-Based Group Discussions

The results of the first working group, which addressed both the lack of a common understanding of climate change and economic viability, are presented below. Results are structured based on the format illustrated in Figure 1, ensuring consistency and clarity in the presentation of findings.

1. Problem Definition

- **What is the specific challenge?**
- **How does climate change affect working conditions and attractiveness?**

The group addressed the complex relationship between climate change, economic viability, and the lack of shared understanding among key actors across the agricultural value chain. While the discussion began with the issue of financial uncertainty for farmers, it quickly broadened to the recognition that perceptions and understanding of climate impacts on

agriculture differ widely among stakeholders—including farmers, consumers, policymakers, and the wider public.

This lack of common understanding contributes to a disconnect between policy design, societal expectations, and farmers lived realities, undermining both social recognition and economic resilience in the sector. Farming was identified as a distinct occupation—largely self-employed, highly exposed to weather variability, and dependent on long-term recovery cycles after extreme events.

Climate-induced risks such as droughts, floods, or storms can have multi-year financial consequences, deepening income instability. When society and policymakers do not fully grasp these realities, it weakens support mechanisms, public empathy, and the perceived attractiveness of farming as a profession.

The group stated that improving societal understanding, trust, and compassion for farmers' experiences is central to building both economic and social sustainability under climate change.

2. Target Group

- **Who is affected (e.g. young farmers, seasonal workers)?**
- **What are their vulnerabilities?**

The discussion identified several interconnected target groups:

- Farmers and farm workers, particularly smallholders and self-employed producers, who face direct economic and emotional impacts from climate-related uncertainty.
- Consumers and citizens, whose limited understanding of agricultural realities influences public discourse and market pressures.
- Policymakers and institutions, whose fragmented perspectives can lead to misaligned interventions or communication gaps.
- The wider rural population, who are indirectly affected by declining farm viability and the erosion of rural livelihoods.

Given that “anyone who eats food is connected to agriculture,” the group underlined the need to engage the entire society in improving understanding of climate impacts on farming and recognising the sector's central role in achieving climate and food security objectives.

3. Policy Gaps

- **What policy measures do we currently have that focus on this issue?**
- **What's missing in current EU/national policies? (Where are the blind spots?)**

The group identified several policy blind spots:

- Lack of integration between climate, agricultural, and social policy frameworks, particularly in communication and education.
- Insufficient recognition of farmers' societal contributions beyond food production, such as environmental stewardship and rural cohesion.
- Inadequate mechanisms for fair value distribution along the supply chain, leaving producers vulnerable to market pressures.

- Limited policy attention to mental health and well-being in rural and agricultural strategies.
- Insufficient flexibility in financial instruments (e.g., CAP payments) to respond to climate-related shocks.
- Absence of systematic public education on food systems and climate.
- Addressing these gaps will require policy integration, enhanced data collection on farmers' financial and social conditions, and communication strategies that make agriculture's role in climate adaptation visible and valued.

4. Proposed Interventions

- **Concrete policy actions (e.g. funding, mental health programs, digital training)**
- **Alignment with EU Vision 2040, CAP, Green Deal.**

A range of interventions was identified to strengthen both economic viability and public understanding:

- Enhance communication and education: Introduce food and farming literacy from an early age to reconnect citizens with the realities of agricultural production. Education campaigns should extend beyond farming communities to reach urban populations, schools, and consumers through public communication and retail networks (e.g., supermarkets).
- Promote positive narratives and trust: Shift the public image of farming from negative associations (e.g., emissions, pesticides) to recognition of its contributions to biodiversity, food security, and rural identity. Public campaigns and media should celebrate “small wins” and good practices in agriculture.
- Introduce flexibility in payment systems: Allow national authorities greater flexibility to adjust CAP payment schedules following extreme weather events to stabilise cash flow and reduce stress for affected farmers.
- Explore a “living wage” concept for agriculture: Recognise the provision of public goods—such as carbon sequestration, biodiversity conservation, and animal welfare—as paid work. Farmers should receive fair and predictable remuneration for these services, ensuring a minimum income baseline like other sectors.
- Foster fairness and transparency in food chains: Support mechanisms linking production costs to consumer prices, promoting transparency and fair returns to producers.
- Support mental health and well-being: Integrate psychosocial support into rural development measures to mitigate the stress linked to financial uncertainty and public scrutiny.

5. Implementation Pathways

- **Concrete policy actions (e.g. funding, mental health programs, digital training)**

— **Alignment with EU Vision 2040, CAP, Green Deal**

Effective implementation requires cross-sectoral coordination and multi-level governance:

- EU level: Embed understanding, communication, and social recognition into existing CAP and Green Deal frameworks. Ensure that DG AGRI, DG EMPL, and DG CLIMA work collaboratively to link climate adaptation, financial resilience, and education strategies.
- National level: Member States should tailor interventions to local contexts, including flexibility in payment timing, national education initiatives, and fair price regulations. Cooperation with the ministries of education, economy, and agriculture is essential to ensure consistency.
- Local and community level: Rural networks, cooperatives, and educational institutions can serve as communication bridges, hosting awareness campaigns and knowledge-sharing events. Partnerships with supermarkets and local markets can help bring climate and farming narratives closer to consumers.
- Private sector and retail actors: Engage the retail sector as active partners in communicating transparent pricing, promoting local produce, and supporting fair-trade mechanisms that value sustainable farming practices.

6. Risks & Barriers

— **Political, cultural, economic, governance or technical obstacles**

— **How to overcome them?**

Key risks and barriers include:

- Persistent misconceptions about farming and its environmental impact, leading to mistrust between producers and the public.
- Fragmented communication between the EU, national and local levels, limiting consistent messaging.
- Structural income insecurity caused by weather variability and market volatility.
- Limited engagement from the retail sector in promoting fair pricing and transparent communication.
- Resistance to change within both farming communities and the general public.
- Social stigma and mental health challenges arising from negative portrayals of farming and financial stress.

Overcoming these barriers requires coordinated communication strategies, stronger inter-sectoral dialogue, and recognition of the psychological dimensions of economic uncertainty.

7. Indicators of Success

— **How will we measure impact?**

— **What metrics (e.g. youth retention, mental health outcomes, tech adoption)?**

The group proposed the following indicators for monitoring progress:

- Improved public understanding of the link between climate change, food production, and farmers' livelihoods (measured through surveys or awareness indexes).
- Reduced financial stress and improved income stability for farmers (e.g., fewer cases of late payments or insolvency linked to climate impacts).
- Enhanced well-being and occupational health, reflected in fewer days lost to illness or injury.
- Increased alignment between CAP payments and delivery of societal value, including ecosystem services.
- More positive media coverage and public sentiment regarding agriculture.
- Active participation of non-farming citizens in educational and community initiatives related to agriculture and climate adaptation.

In addition, the discussion on Lack of Common Understanding of Climate Change and Economic Viability highlighted the need to align perception, policy, and practice to strengthen the resilience of European agriculture. Climate change threatens not only farm productivity but also exposes gaps in how farmers, policymakers, and the public understand and value agricultural work. Participants agreed that economic viability and social recognition are interlinked, calling for better education, fair value chains, flexible payments, and stronger social protection. Building shared understanding and trust will help position farmers as key partners in climate solutions and ensure that farming remains a viable and respected profession in a changing climate.

The results of the II work group (Group II), discussing about the Policy integration with a focus on social protection in the context of climate change and farming are presented below.

1. Problem Definition

- **What is the specific challenge?**
- **How does climate change affect working conditions and attractiveness?**

The group examined the broader policy implications of climate change for the social and economic dimensions of farming, acknowledging the interdependence of market, social, and health systems in the agricultural sector. Although the focus was on social aspects, it was recognised that market mechanisms within the CAP play a major social role by providing income stability for farmers. The CAP, while historically designed as a market instrument to ensure food security, increasingly intersects with social policy areas such as health, well-being, and income protection. The group identified three main issues underpinning farmers' working and living conditions:

- The market system, providing income support and stability.
- The social protection system, covering employment, social security, and labour rights.
- The occupational safety and health (OSH) system encompassing both physical and mental health.

Climate change acts as a multiplier of existing vulnerabilities, worsening income instability, occupational risks, and rural depopulation. It also undermines the sector's attractiveness, particularly for younger generations, due to increased uncertainty, harsher working conditions, and lower perceived social recognition.

2. Target Group

- **Who is affected (e.g. young farmers, seasonal workers) and what are their vulnerabilities?**

Two principal target groups were identified:

- Self-employed farmers, including family farmers and micro-producers. These actors often fall outside conventional social protection schemes and depend largely on market mechanisms for income security. A subgroup of micro-producers was noted — individuals who produce limited quantities of food, sometimes while officially registered as unemployed. Their contribution to local food systems remains undervalued and insufficiently recognised in policy frameworks.
- Agricultural workers, including migrant, seasonal, and temporary labourers. These groups are generally dependent on employment-related social systems and are particularly exposed to precarious work, limited access to healthcare, and poor OSH conditions.

The discussion also highlighted rural populations more broadly, including non-farm residents whose livelihoods are linked to agricultural activity. Their access to healthcare, mobility, and basic services is crucial for maintaining the social fabric of rural areas.

3. Policy Gaps

- **What policy measures do we currently have that focus on this issue?**
- **What's missing in current EU/national policies? (Where are the blind spots?)**

The discussion identified several critical policy gaps:

- Legal coverage: Significant gaps exist in OSH, pension, and social protection frameworks for self-employed farmers and certain categories of workers.
- Data deficits: Lack of consistent data on farm demographics, employment conditions, and social protection coverage undermines effective policy design.
- Definitions and classifications: Ambiguities in defining "farmer," "worker," and "self-employed" complicate monitoring and policymaking.
- Youth entry and retention: Despite multiple initiatives, policies have not effectively improved generational renewal.
- Uneven national implementation: Devolution of CAP responsibilities to Member States risks creating disparities and undermining minimum social standards.
- Limited integration of OSH in climate policies: Agricultural working conditions under extreme weather remain under-addressed.

Addressing these gaps requires harmonised minimum social standards across Member States, better data collection, and more integrated policymaking connecting agriculture, employment, and social welfare systems.

4. Proposed Interventions

- **Concrete policy actions (e.g. funding, mental health programs, digital training)**
- **Alignment with EU Vision 2040, CAP, Green Deal**

Several interventions were proposed:

- Improved access to finance and land for young and new entrants. The European Investment Bank (EIB)'s role in facilitating loans to young farmers through national intermediaries was welcomed, though concerns remain regarding national implementation and equitable access.
- Development of crop-loss insurance schemes, drawing on examples from France and Spain, to stabilise incomes without over-subsidising the insurance sector.
- Strengthened social protection systems for self-employed and small-scale farmers, ensuring adequate coverage for pensions, health, and occupational risks.
- Incentives for generational renewal, including potential CAP payment adjustments to encourage retirement transitions and land transfers to younger farmers.
- Enhancement of rural living conditions, including better access to healthcare, education, and services, to make rural life more attractive.
- Integration of OSH measures into climate adaptation strategies, ensuring farmers and workers are protected from extreme weather and related health risks.
- Promotion of gender equality and inclusiveness, with attention to women's specific needs in financing and training, building on positive examples from Spain.
- Support for relief services to allow farmers time for training, innovation, and rest, improving work-life balance and sectoral sustainability.

5. Implementation Pathways

- **Who should lead (EU, national, local)?**
- **What channels (Agri, Regio, Employ)?**
- **What resources are needed?**

The group emphasised that the CAP is not a social protection system, yet it increasingly carries social implications. Greater coordination is required between agricultural, employment, and social policy frameworks at the EU and national levels to avoid "siloes" policymaking.

Implementation should follow a multi-level governance approach:

- EU level: Set minimum social and OSH standards across Member States and foster coherence among DG AGRI, DG EMPL, and DG REGIO.

- National level: Tailor implementation to local needs, ensuring equitable treatment and capacity for enforcement. Differences in national priorities may otherwise lead to inconsistent social protection and unfair competition between farmers across Member States.
- Local level: Address land access issues, support community-based solutions, and strengthen service delivery in rural regions.

Cross-sectoral collaboration and data sharing between institutions are essential for coherent implementation.

6. Risks & Barriers

- **Political, cultural, economic, governance or technical obstacles**
- **How to overcome them?**

Key risks and barriers identified include:

- Perception and engagement barriers: Many farmers feel unfairly blamed for environmental degradation, reducing their willingness to engage in climate adaptation. Older farmers are less inclined to adopt new practices.
- Generational renewal challenges: Older farmers often delay retirement, limiting opportunities for new entrants.
- Financial and land access constraints: Limited collateral and risk perception by banks make agriculture less attractive for investment.
- Climate change as a financial risk: Financial institutions increasingly view farming as a high-risk sector, reducing loan availability.
- Rural depopulation: Limited services and harsh working conditions deter youth and families.
- Governance fragmentation: Lack of cross-sectoral cooperation and inconsistent national policies impede progress.
- Market concentration risks: Potential takeover of small family farms by large corporations or financial actors, threatening social cohesion and local food sovereignty.

7. Indicators of Success

- **How will we measure impact?**
- **What metrics (e.g. youth retention, mental health outcomes, tech adoption)?**

Success should be assessed through measurable outcomes reflecting both social and environmental sustainability:

- Number and retention of new entrants in farming, with particular attention to youth and women.
- Improved income stability and reduction in income loss due to climate-related shocks.

- Enhanced OSH performance, including reduced accidents and improved mental health outcomes.
- Effective uptake of European Investment Bank (EIB) and other financing instruments at the national level.
- Progress in inter-DG coordination and cross-sectoral cooperation within the EU framework.
- Improved living conditions in rural areas, including healthcare access and infrastructure.

In addition, the work of Group II on Policy integration with a focus on social protection in the context of climate change and farming highlighted that climate change is not only an environmental challenge but also a social and structural one, deeply affecting the well-being and appeal of the agricultural sector. Participants stressed that farmers’ working conditions and the sector’s long-term sustainability depend on the balance between market mechanisms, social protection, and occupational safety and health. While the CAP provides crucial income support, it was not designed as a social protection tool, underscoring the need for stronger integration between agricultural, employment, and social policies. Strengthening social protection, improving access to land and finance, and enhancing OSH standards were identified as key to building a fair, sustainable, and attractive farming sector under climate change. To support clearer interpretation of the workshop results, a Cross-Group Analysis was conducted to compare the findings of both deep-dive groups (see Table 3).

Table 3. Summary of Group Discussions

Dimension	Group I: Lack of Common Understanding of Climate Change & Economic Viability	Group II: Policy Integration with Social Protection in the Context of Climate Change & Farming
Main Focus	Societal understanding, perception gaps, economic viability.	Structural policy gaps, social protection, OSH, and generational renewal.
Core Problem	Misalignment between public perceptions, policymaking, and farmers lived realities; lack of shared understanding of climate impacts.	Fragmented and inadequate social protection and OSH frameworks for farmers and workers under climate stress.
How Climate Change Affects the Sector	Increases financial and emotional stress, reduces social recognition, weakens attractiveness.	Multiplies vulnerabilities by increasing income instability, health risks, and rural depopulation.
Target Groups	Farmers, farm workers, consumers, policymakers, rural communities.	Self-employed farmers, micro-producers, agricultural workers (incl. seasonal & migrant), rural populations.
Key Vulnerabilities Identified	Income instability, poor public understanding, negative societal narratives, mental health stress.	Gaps in social protection, OSH deficits, precarious employment

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		conditions, barriers for youth and women.
Policy Gaps Highlighted	Lack of integrated communication, weak recognition of farmers' contributions, inflexible CAP tools, missing food system literacy.	Gaps in legal coverage, data deficits, unclear definitions of farmers/worker categories, uneven national implementation.
Main Interventions Proposed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strengthen communication & education - Promote positive narratives - Flexible CAP payment schedules - Living wage for ecosystem services - Fair value chains - Mental health support 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social protection reforms - Better access to finance & land - Crop-loss insurance - OSH integration into climate policies - Gender-responsive measures - Rural services improvement - Retirement/land transfer incentives
Implementation Priorities	Multi-level coordination; communication bridges via rural networks & retailers; public engagement through education.	Harmonised EU social & OSH standards; inter-DG coordination; national enforcement; local solutions for land access & services.
Risks & Barriers	Misconceptions about farming; fragmented communication; structural income insecurity; social stigma; public mistrust.	Financial risk perception of agriculture; generational renewal gap; governance fragmentation; rural depopulation; market concentration risks.
Success Indicators	Public understanding metrics; income stability; improved well-being; fairer value chains; positive media coverage; participation in food literacy.	Youth & women's retention; income stability; reduced accidents & improved mental health; uptake of finance tools; cross-sectoral coordination; better rural services.
Underlying Insight	Economic viability and social recognition depend on bridging perception gaps and building empathy between society and farmers.	Farming resilience requires integration across agricultural, social, employment and OSH systems to ensure fairness and long-term sustainability.

The comparative table highlights that, while the two groups examined different entry points—public understanding and economic viability (Group I) versus policy integration and social protection (Group II)—their analyses converge on several core issues. Both groups underscore that climate change intensifies existing vulnerabilities in the agricultural sector, affecting income stability, working conditions, and the long-term attractiveness of farming. Group I emphasised societal perception, communication gaps, and the need for fair value distribution, whereas Group II identified structural deficits in social protection, occupational safety and health, and generational renewal. Taken together, the findings demonstrate that enhancing resilience in farming requires coordinated action across social, economic, and policy domains, supported by coherent governance and improved recognition of agriculture's role in climate adaptation.

4.4. Summary of Policy Actions Identified by Hackathon Participants

The work of Day 2, in addition to providing a first synthesis of reflections and key findings from Day 1, sought to identify and develop a high-level summary of policy actions, which were highlighted by the participants on Day 1, see below. During Day 2 discussions, the SafeHabitus team mapped the actions emerging from Day 1 group work against current and proposed EU policy proposals. This mapping exercise, though preliminary, served multiple purposes:

Validation of Stakeholder Priorities: The exercise identified substantial alignment between stakeholder-identified needs and the strategic direction of CAP reform, particularly regarding flexibility, generational renewal, and integrated governance. This demonstrates that the bottom-up, evidence-based methodology employed in the hackathon arrived at priorities consistent with high-level policy developments. This validates both the participatory process and the policy relevance of findings. There are, however, important caveats with concerns raised that greater flexibility could result in diminished focus on social sustainability concerns, in particular generational renewal.

Identification of Implementation Opportunities: By considering specific CAP instruments and delivery mechanisms, the team identified concrete entry points where hackathon actions could be operationalised within the emerging policy. For example, recommendations regarding flexible payment timing following extreme weather events aligned with the territorial approach and enhanced Member State autonomy, while proposals for young farmer support linked directly with the generational renewal toolbox proposal.

Recognition of Policy Gaps: Critically, the mapping process also revealed areas where the CAP proposals did not adequately address stakeholder concerns. Most notably, while environmental farm stewardship is a feature of current CAP proposals, explicit integration of occupational health and safety (OSH) measures within climate adaptation strategies remained largely absent.

4.4.1 Policy Actions

The hackathon identified policy actions across multiple governance levels, addressing key gaps in current frameworks while reinforcing progressive elements of the CAP post-2027 proposals. These actions, presented below, were developed through subsequent assessment of materials developed on the day including roadmaps, notes and discussion transcripts, are organised by the level at which action is required.

EU Level

Action EU-1: Establish an EU Working Group on Agricultural OSH and Climate Adaptation

Establish a dedicated working group bringing together DG AGRI, DG EMPL, DG CLIMA, and EU-OSHA to assess the feasibility of EU-wide occupational safety and health standards for agriculture that explicitly integrate climate-related protections (heat stress protocols, extreme weather safety measures, ergonomic adaptations). This addresses the current gap where environmental farm stewardship is emphasised but worker protection from climate hazards remains unaddressed.

Action EU-2: Launch an EU-Wide Public Education Initiative on Farming's Role in Climate Solutions

Develop and implement a comprehensive communication strategy, coordinated by DG AGRI, DG ENV, and DG EAC, to improve public understanding of farming's contributions to climate adaptation and food security, including integration of agricultural literacy into school curricula and sustained multimedia engagement targeting both urban and non-farming rural communities.

EU/National Level

Action EN-1: Introduce Flexible CAP Payment Mechanisms Following Extreme Weather Events

Enable Member States to adjust CAP payment schedules or advance payments when farmers experience documented extreme weather impacts, utilising the territorial approach and enhanced Member State autonomy in CAP post-2027. This addresses the cash flow disruptions that compound climate shock vulnerability during critical recovery periods.

Action EN-2: Ensure Coordinated Multi-Sectoral Approaches to Climate Adaptation

Establish formal coordination mechanisms at EU level (inter-DG working groups) and encourage Member States to create inter-ministerial bodies ensuring that climate adaptation strategies integrate agricultural market tools, social protection measures, and OSH standards coherently, avoiding siloed policy development.

National Level

Action N-1: Develop or Expand Accessible National Production Insurance Schemes

Establish or significantly expand production-loss insurance schemes adapted to climate risks (drought, flood, heatwave, storms), ensuring accessibility for small-scale farmers through subsidised premiums, simplified application processes, and adequate coverage. Build on successful models from France and Spain while adapting to regional contexts.

Action N-2: Establish National Farmer Mental Health Support Programmes

Support comprehensive farmer mental health support programmes that recognise psychological wellbeing as integral to agricultural resilience, including climate-specific components addressing environmental uncertainty stress. Ensure accessible service delivery through integration with rural health systems and agricultural advisory services, peer support networks.

National / Regional Level

Action NR-1: Implement Farm Relief Services Enabling Work-Life Balance and Professional Development

Develop and implement farm relief service programmes allowing farmers to access temporary replacement labour for illness or injury, maternity leave, family care, holidays, and education/training participation. Establish pools of trained agricultural workers and accessible service delivery models, underpinned by sustainable financing through a combination of CAP supports and user fees.

Action NR-2: Strengthen Comprehensive Rural Service Delivery to Enhance Farming Attractiveness

Support improvement of rural service delivery across healthcare access, education and childcare availability, transport infrastructure, digital connectivity, and social/cultural infrastructure. Utilise the integrated NRPP framework to enable synergistic investments across agriculture and territorial development, addressing the reality that farming attractiveness depends fundamentally on rural quality of life.

5. Policy Implications: Supporting and Extending the CAP Post-2027 Framework

The policy actions identified from the hackathon provide an opportunity to examine alignment between stakeholder-identified priorities and the current proposals for the Common Agricultural Policy post-2027, published in July 2025 (COM(2025) 560 final). This section provides a summary assessment of how the hackathon findings relate to the proposed CAP framework, identifying areas where recommendations align with and build upon existing provisions, as well as areas where critical gaps remain.

The analysis reveals significant alignment between the priorities identified through participatory stakeholder engagement and the reforms that have been proposed. This suggests that bottom-up, evidence-based policy development and top-down policy reform can arrive at similar conclusions when both engage with agricultural realities under climate change. However, the analysis also identifies some gaps—particularly regarding occupational safety and health coverage for self-employed farmers and the integration of climate-specific protections—where current proposals inadequately address the challenges documented in D4.1, D4.2, D4.3, and confirmed through hackathon deliberations.

5.1. Policy Context: The CAP Post-2027 Framework

The Commission's CAP post-2027 proposals represent a substantial shift toward simplification, flexibility, and integration. Key features of the proposed framework include:

Enhanced Member State Flexibility: A central principle of the post-2027 CAP is the territorial approach, which grants Member States significantly more autonomy to design interventions tailored to regional and sectoral specificities. Rather than EU-level conditionalities, the Commission have proposed providing national recommendations to guide Member State planning, while maintaining common objectives and a level playing field (European Commission, 2025c). This approach aims to accommodate the diversity of European farming systems and enables more responsive policy design suited to local climate, economic, and social conditions.

Generational Renewal Emphasis: The proposals provide provisions for support for young farmers through multiple mechanisms, though, it should be noted that these are not ringfenced. A 6% aspirational target at EU level directs resources toward generational renewal, with dedicated instruments including enhanced area-based payments, a "starter pack" of tailored support measures, and improved access to land, credit, and training (European Commission, 2025c). Recognising that farming attractiveness depends on broader rural quality of life, the framework also encourages Member States to invest in rural

connectivity, essential services, childcare, and skills development to make rural areas appealing places to live and work.

Farm Stewardship and Environmental Measures: The CAP post-2027 introduces a new farm stewardship system which aims to provide a more balanced approach between obligations and incentives, with simplified, territorially adapted requirements for income support recipients. Instead of "one-size-fits-all" measures, Member States design stewardship practices suited to local environmental conditions, guided by Commission recommendations to ensure collective achievement of EU environmental and climate objectives (European Commission, 2025a).

Crisis Resilience and Risk Management: Responding to increased volatility from climate change and geopolitical uncertainties, the proposals establish a Unity Safety Net with ring-fenced funding for the seven-year period—effectively doubling the crisis reserve available under current arrangements. This enhanced buffer aims to support farmers facing market disturbances while encouraging uptake of risk management tools and on-farm resilience measures (European Commission, 2025b).

5.2 Summary: Mapping Recommendations to CAP Post-2027 Provisions

Table 4 provides a systematic mapping of hackathon-derived recommendations to relevant CAP post-2027 provisions, distinguishing between recommendations that align with and build upon existing proposals and those that address identified gaps.

Table 4. Mapping of D4.4 Recommendations to CAP Post-2027 Provisions

Recommendation	CAP Article(s)	Relationship	Assessment
EU-1: EU Working Group on Agricultural OSH Standards	Articles 3, 4	Gap	Article 3 incorporates OSH through SMRs 12-14, but these exclude self-employed farmers; climate-specific protections absent
EU-2: EU Public Education Initiative	Articles 19, 20	Partial Alignment	AKIS framework enables knowledge dissemination; recommendation extends to broader public engagement
EN-1: Flexible CAP Payment Mechanisms	Article 6	Gap	No provision for payment schedule adjustment following climate shocks

Recommendation	CAP Article(s)	Relationship	Assessment
EN-2: Coordinated Multi-Sectoral Approaches	Article 2, NRPP framework	Enabling	National recommendations mechanism and NRPP enable coordination; recommendation emphasises explicit mechanisms
N-1: National Crop-Loss Insurance Schemes	Article 12	Alignment	Article 12 provides framework; recommendation emphasises accessibility for small-scale farmers
N-2: National Farmer Mental Health Programmes	Article 20(3)(a)	Alignment with Strengthening	Article 20 explicitly includes mental health awareness; recommendation calls for comprehensive dedicated programmes
N-3: Land and Finance Access for Young Farmers	Articles 14, 15, 16	Strong Alignment	Comprehensive young farmer framework: recommendation emphasises effective implementation
NR-1: Farm Relief Services	Article 17, Article 16(1)(i)	Strong Alignment	Article 17 directly enables; permissive formulation creates implementation challenges
NR-2: Strengthen Rural Service Delivery	Article 18, NRPP framework	Alignment	LEADER and NRPP enable integrated territorial development

5.3 Strategic Implications

The analysis demonstrates that D4.4 findings both validate and extend the CAP post-2027 framework. Substantial alignments on generational renewal, relief services, mental health awareness, risk management, and integrated governance suggest that participatory, evidence-based research and policy reform can converge on similar priorities when both genuinely engage with agricultural realities under climate change. This convergence enhances the credibility of both processes.

The identification of critical gaps—OSH coverage and climate integration, payment flexibility mechanisms, and social protection coordination—indicates that current proposals, while progressive in many respects, do not fully address the full spectrum of climate-related occupational challenges facing European farmers and agricultural workers. These gaps are

not merely technical omissions but reflect deeper questions about agricultural policy's scope and its relationship to employment, social, and health policy domains.

For EU Institutions: The identified gaps represent opportunities for targeted amendments during legislative negotiations or for inclusion in Commission recommendations guiding Member State plan development. Addressing OSH coverage exclusions, climate-specific protections, and coordination mechanisms would strengthen the framework's capacity to deliver on stated objectives of resilient, attractive, and sustainable agriculture.

For Member States: The National Rural Policy Plan framework's flexibility creates space for innovation. Member States could pilot relief services (utilising Article 17), establish comprehensive mental health programmes (building on Article 20), or create OSH-climate coordination mechanisms, potentially establishing best practices that inform future EU-level provisions.

For Stakeholders: The alignment between hackathon recommendations and CAP directions strengthens advocacy positions. Stakeholders can frame proposals for addressing identified gaps not as opposition to CAP reform but as essential strengthening measures ensuring the framework achieves its stated objectives.

For Researchers: The D4.4 findings demonstrate the value of policy-engaged research that situates empirical findings within evolving policy contexts. Future SafeHabitus work, particularly policy brief development for MS15, will build on the resources and evidence developed through the process of preparing for and undertaking the hackathon, and utilise the analyses presented in this report.

Conclusion

The literature review indicates that anticipating pathways to the future of farming under climate change requires an integrated and systemic approach. Evidence highlights that the impacts of climate change on working conditions and the attractiveness of farming are multidimensional, affecting employed and self-employed farmers as well as new entrants. Addressing these challenges necessitates coordinated policy action, combining economic support, access to locally targeted knowledge, innovation and digital tools, mental health and social services, and improved occupational safety. Strengthening these dimensions is essential to enhance the resilience of the agricultural workforce and to ensure that farming remains a sustainable, safe, and attractive profession in the long term.

The Hackathon provided a collaborative platform to explore how climate change affects future working conditions and the attractiveness of farming. By engaging diverse stakeholders in structured dialogue and co-creation, the event generated valuable insights for policy development and identified key priorities for building a more resilient and sustainable agricultural workforce.

The two group discussions working on the topics of *Lack of Common Understanding of Climate Change and Economic Viability* and *Policy integration, with a focus on social protection in the context of climate change and farming*, converged on a shared recognition that climate change is transforming not only the economics of farming but also its social foundations. Both groups highlighted that future working conditions and the attractiveness of farming depend on strengthening the links between economic viability, social protection, and public understanding.

While the theoretical analysis identified digital innovation and technology as one of the key areas of research focus, it is noteworthy that this topic did not emerge as a central theme during the group discussions at the hackathon. This gap suggests a potential disconnect between academic discourse and stakeholder priorities on the ground, highlighting the need for further exploration of how digital tools can be better integrated into practical solutions for climate-resilient farming.

A central finding is that farmers' financial security, well-being, and social recognition are deeply interconnected. Climate change amplifies uncertainties in income, health, and working conditions, while limited societal understanding and fragmented policies further undermine the sector's attractiveness. Addressing these challenges requires integrated policymaking that bridges agricultural, social, and climate frameworks at EU and national levels.

Key priorities identified include:

- Improving communication and education to build societal trust and appreciation of farming's role in climate solutions.

- Enhancing social protection and OSH for farmers and agricultural workers.
- Ensuring fair economic conditions through access to land, finance, and transparent value chains.
- Fostering generational renewal and gender equality, making farming an appealing career path for young people.

Together, the two discussions emphasised that Europe's agricultural future relies not only on economic and financial security and viability but also on social resilience, fair policy integration, and a renewed public contract between farmers and society. By strengthening understanding, solidarity, and protection, the agricultural sector can remain both economically viable and socially sustainable in the era of climate change.

The policy actions identified from the two working groups highlight the need for coordinated action across multiple governance levels. At EU level, the emphasis is on improving occupational safety and health, strengthening public understanding of farming's role in climate adaptation, and enhancing coherence across policy domains. Actions at the EU-national interface focus on increasing flexibility within Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) payment systems and ensuring better integration between climate, social protection, and OSH measures. At national level, the priority is to improve risk-management tools such as production-loss insurance, expand mental-health support for farmers, and address structural barriers related to land and finance for young entrants. Finally, at local and sectoral levels, the recommendations call for practical support measures—such as respite services and strengthened rural infrastructure—to enhance farmers' well-being and the overall attractiveness of rural areas. Together, these actions respond directly to the vulnerabilities identified by both Working Groups.

Next Steps

- The results generated through the hackathon, including the key insights, priority challenges, and policy recommendations, will now be shared across all Communities of Practice to ensure broad dissemination, collective reflection, and validation. Each community will be invited to review the findings, provide feedback based on their specific expertise and regional contexts, and identify any additional considerations relevant to their work. This collaborative validation process will help refine the outcomes, strengthen their relevance for diverse agricultural settings, and ensure alignment with ongoing initiatives under the project.
- The outcomes of this work will directly support WP6 by feeding into the development of the policy brief(s) and ensuring that recommendations are grounded in the insights generated through the hackathon.
- The results of the hackathon will be disseminated widely through multiple communication channels to ensure broad outreach and engagement. Key findings will be presented at relevant scientific conferences (and shared through a dedicated newsletter on the SafeHabitus website), as well as across the project's social media platforms, including LinkedIn. In addition, dissemination will extend through partner

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networks helping to reach farming communities, policy stakeholders, and academic audiences. Further visibility will be supported through upcoming webinars and online events, enabling continued dialogue and knowledge exchange across all Communities of Practice.

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Annex 1: Use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the Synthesis of Hackathon Outputs

How artificial intelligence (AI) Supported the Synthesis of Hackathon Outputs

The SafeHabitus policy hackathon generated a substantial amount of qualitative data through interactive sessions, including pair discussions, thematic clustering, and roadmap-based group work. To ensure that these insights were captured accurately and presented systematically, a multi-step process was applied:

Human-Led Documentation and Audio Recording

Dedicated note-takers documented discussions in detail during all workshop sessions. In addition, audio recordings were made—with informed consent from participants—to capture nuances and ensure completeness of the dialogue. These recordings served as a reference point for validating and enriching the written notes, reducing the risk of omissions or misinterpretations.

AI-Assisted Synthesis and Structuring

Following the hackathon, AI tools were employed to support the authors in organising and synthesising the extensive documentation. The authors first extracted the transcript of each recording and fully anonymised the text to ensure that no identifiable information remained. As we were not interested in who specifically said what, anonymisation followed a simple format, i.e. PS_1 = Policy Stakeholder1, R_1 = Researcher 1, and PT_1 = Practitioner 1. No information regarding country, gender or equivalent information remained.

The AI was instructed to:

1. **Aggregate and Consolidate Inputs**

Merge contributions from multiple sources into coherent summaries, preserving the original meaning and tone of participant insights.

2. **Identify Patterns and Organize Themes**

Systematically group related ideas, highlight recurring concepts, and align them with the predefined analytical framework (e.g., problem definition, policy gaps, proposed interventions).

3. **Enhance Clarity and Consistency**

Refine language for readability and ensure consistent terminology across sections, while maintaining authenticity.

4. **Support Data Presentation**

Assist in creating structured tables and figures that reflect the diversity of stakeholder inputs, making the results accessible and suitable for inclusion in the report.

Preservation of Authenticity

Throughout this process, AI tools were used strictly for structuring and clarity enhancement. No new content was introduced; all insights originated from hackathon participants and were validated by the authors. The AI acted as a facilitator for transforming raw notes and audio transcripts into a well-organised, evidence-based narrative.

Outcome

This combined approach—human documentation, audio recording, and AI-assisted synthesis—enabled the report to present complex, multi-actor discussions in a clear, systematic, and policy-relevant format, while preserving the authenticity of stakeholder voices. Consistent with the methodology described in the this report, transcripts derived from audio recordings were fully anonymised and used solely to support thematic aggregation and synthesis; no verbatim quotations or attribution of individual statements were generated or retained.

Annex 2: Detailed overview of key challenges identified at the hackathon

- 1.** The absence of a shared understanding of climate change across different levels (EU, national, and local) —as well as among farmers and the wider public. This fragmentation impedes collective action and weakens the sector’s ability to respond coherently to climate pressures. Participants highlighted that rising production costs and volatile markets further strain farmers’ economic viability. Low-income levels and what is considered to be unfair competition make farming unattractive, to new entrants.
- 2.** The insufficient integration of agricultural, social, and employment policies to address the social consequences of climate change in farming. While the CAP provides essential income support, it does not, nor was it designed to, function as a social protection instrument. This means that many farmers and agricultural workers are left without adequate coverage in the event of loss of income or the costs of recovering following extreme weather events. Fragmented responsibilities between the EU, national, and local levels, combined with limited coordination across policy areas, hinder the development of coherent responses to climate-related risks. As a result, gaps in social security, occupational safety, and health systems persist—undermining farmers’ resilience, discouraging generational renewal, and threatening the long-term sustainability and attractiveness of rural livelihoods.
- 3.** Financial insecurity and generational renewal, stressing that climate change is intensifying financial insecurity in the agricultural sector. Increasingly frequent droughts, wildfires, and other extreme weather events lead to financial losses and longer-term income instability. While insurance systems can partly mitigate these risks, existing mechanisms are, in some instances, insufficient to ensure stability for all farmers, particularly those with smaller holdings. This growing uncertainty adversely affects generational renewal within the sector. Young people are becoming reluctant to pursue farming careers when they observe recurring impacts and, associated with this, high stress levels linked to growing uncertainty regarding income, workload and future climatic conditions. As a result, the social sustainability of, particularly family farming and the continuity of agricultural communities are undermined, threatening the long-term resilience of rural areas and, ultimately, food security.
- 4.** Insufficient insurance and support mechanisms. Participants pointed out that farmers require more comprehensive insurance and support systems to strengthen their resilience to climate-related risks. Existing schemes often fail to address the full scope of challenges linked to extreme weather, health pressures, and workload intensity. Examples such as Finland’s farmer (social) support programmes, which include medical and health insurance as well as respite services enabling farmers to take holidays, demonstrate good practice in

supporting well-being within the sector. Similarly, drought insurance and compensation mechanisms for lost production are essential tools for stabilising income and enabling recovery and reinvestment after climate-induced losses. Expanding access to such instruments and linking them with resources for implementing climate adaptation measures would help farmers better counteract the impacts of climate change and ensure the long-term viability of rural livelihoods.

5. Public perceptions and understanding about farming. Effective communication is essential to strengthen the social perception of farming and promote agriculture as part of the climate solution. The sector's role in sustainable food production and environmental stewardship is often underrepresented, leading to a distorted public image and weakening trust between farmers and society. Communicating the positive contributions of sustainable farming, animal welfare improvements, and adaptation to climate change can help rebuild this connection and attract new generations to the sector.

6. Economic insecurity and occupational risks of agricultural workers. Farm workers face growing economic and occupational vulnerabilities linked to climate change. Earnings in the agricultural sector are, on average, around 40% lower than in other sectors, and climate-induced production losses further reduce income stability. Rising temperatures, droughts, and extreme weather also increase physical and mental health risks for those working outdoors. Self-employed farmers, who represent a large share of the workforce, often fall through protection gaps in existing social and occupational safety frameworks. Current EU and national directives remain largely generic, rarely addressing climate-related risks such as heat stress, nor ensuring adequate coverage for agricultural workers.

7. Farmer mental health and value recognition. Economic insecurity in agriculture extends beyond financial instability, increasingly affecting the social fabric of rural communities. Climate-induced losses and volatile markets undermine not only farmers' livelihoods but also their sense of continuity and belonging. This uncertainty makes it difficult for the younger generation to envisage a stable and fulfilling future in farming. Without stronger social cohesion, reliable income, and long-term policy support, generational renewal will be further challenged which in turn could undermine rural vitality and sustainability. Ensuring that young people can see a socially and economically viable and respected future in agriculture is essential for the sustainability of food production and the resilience of European rural societies.

8. Socio-economic insecurity and the future of the younger generation. Economic insecurity in agriculture extends beyond financial instability, increasingly affecting the social fabric of rural communities. Climate-induced losses and volatile markets undermine not only farmers' livelihoods but also their sense of continuity and belonging. This uncertainty makes it difficult for the younger generation to envisage a stable and fulfilling future in farming. Without stronger social cohesion, reliable income perspectives, and long-term policy support, rural areas risk depopulation and a loss of generational renewal. Ensuring that young people can see a viable and respected future in agriculture is essential for the sustainability of food production and the resilience of European rural societies.

9. Interconnected impacts on health, well-being and work–life balance. The effects of climate change on agriculture are deeply interconnected with broader issues of health, well-being, and social stability at both national and regional levels. Changing environmental conditions affect not only physical working environments but also mental health, community cohesion, and quality of life in rural areas. As farmers face growing workloads, financial uncertainty, and environmental stress, maintaining a healthy work–life balance becomes increasingly difficult. These dynamics demonstrate that climate adaptation in agriculture must be addressed holistically, integrating social, health, and labour dimensions to build truly sustainable and resilient rural systems.

10. Managing uncertainty in farming operations. Farmers must increasingly manage uncertainty on a daily and seasonal basis, as unpredictable weather patterns and market fluctuations become the new normal. These short-term disruptions directly affect the organisation and viability of farm businesses—complicating planning, investment, and labour management. Over time, the cumulative effect of uncertainty also undermines social and economic stability within rural communities, eroding confidence in the future of the sector. Strengthening farmers’ capacity to anticipate and adapt to change is therefore essential, both to maintain business continuity and to safeguard the long-term resilience of agricultural livelihoods.

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